

REPROCESSABLE HIGH PERFORMANCE EPOXY IMINE VITRIMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Vitrimers retain the structural integrity of thermosets while exhibiting flow-like properties under certain conditions, enabled by heat-activated dynamic bond exchange reactions. In this study, the effects of off-stoichiometric ratios in tailoring the properties and reprocessability of imine-epoxy vitrimers, focusing on a para-substituted imine-epoxy vitrimer is studied and compared to a standard thermoset based upon diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A. Furthermore, this work enabled an exploration of transimination—secondary bond exchange reaction where imine groups interact with unreacted amines—alongside imine metathesis. Stoichiometric balance starting from epoxy excess to amine excess were systematically varied to explore the impact upon static thermal and mechanical properties, as well as dynamic behaviour including the temperature of vitrification (T_v), adhesion, malleability and remouldability. These findings highlight how off-stoichiometric designs can optimize repairability and durability in highly aromatic epoxy vitrimers through dynamic imine chemistry, advancing the development of sustainable, reprocessable composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Vitrimers are covalently crosslinked polymer networks modified with dynamic or reversible bonds capable of undergoing bond exchange reactions. These reactions enable topological rearrangements within the network without compromising the overall crosslink density.[1] The exchange can be triggered by external stimuli such as changes in temperature, pH, light, or the presence of chemical additives.[2-4] Examples of dynamic bonds commonly used in vitrimers include ester bonds, boronic esters, imines, and disulfide linkages.[5] As a result of the dynamic behavior, vitrimers can exhibit thermoplastic-like flow under specific conditions, a property not inherent in conventional thermosets, offering advantages in terms of recyclability, remouldability, and repair after curing.[6, 7]

Imines are particularly attractive due to their thermally activated bond exchange reactions and catalyst-free reprocessing. They undergo two types of bond exchange reactions, i.e., imine metathesis, which involves exchange between imine groups, and transimination, which occurs through reaction with free amine groups.[8] Since amine-based hardeners are commonly used in epoxy networks, varying the amine-to-epoxide stoichiometry can influence the amount of unreacted amine groups present in the cured network. These residual amines may participate in transimination reactions with imine bonds, not only during reprocessing but potentially during the curing process itself. This raises the question of how stoichiometry influences not only the curing process but also the post-cure properties and reprocessability of imine-based vitrimers. While off-stoichiometric formulations are

typically avoided in traditional thermosets due to their negative impact on thermal and mechanical properties, vitrimers may tolerate or even benefit from such formulations. Investigating this could provide valuable insights into how vitrimers differ from conventional thermosets, especially in terms of thermal and mechanical properties, reprocessability, and hydrolytic stability.

The role of stoichiometry in crosslinked polymers, particularly epoxy amine networks has been studied for many years and the relationships are well understood.[9-12] For the best combination of mechanical, thermal and physical properties, a stoichiometric, or small epoxide group excess is typically used because it will produce a homogenous network and provide the best opportunity for complete cure and a minimum of remaining reactive groups. Recent examples of systematic studies on epoxy networks and epoxy vitrimers include Senanayake et al. (2024) that reported on the impact of stoichiometry on the properties of epoxy/acid thermosets.[13] Jing and Xie (2022) investigated the effect of stoichiometry on the properties and reprocessability of epoxy/acid vitrimers facilitated by Zn²⁺-catalyzed transesterification which was the first type of vitrimer reported. They varied the epoxy-fatty acid ratio and obtained glass transition temperatures between 20°C and 30°C and tensile strength between 2 to 4 MPa that decrease with increasing epoxy/acid ratio due to decreasing crosslink density.[14] Sheng and Guo (2023) did a similar study, varying the epoxy/acid ratio and found that the epoxy content increased glass transition temperature due to higher proportion of the rigid aromatic epoxide backbone from 40°C to 63°C and increased tensile strength increased from 26 to 43 MPa. In terms of reparability using a scratch test, increasing epoxy content enhanced reparability highlighting the importance of stoichiometry. [15]

In this work, an imine epoxy resin synthesized in house has been cured with diethyl toluene diamine (DETDA) using a range of stoichiometries from epoxy to amine excess and characterized for their static and dynamic properties. Various thermal, thermomechanical, and mechanical techniques were used to compare and contrast the dynamic network compared with a traditional epoxy amine network. Key dynamic properties such as material flow, topology freezing temperature, activation energy of dynamic behaviour, stress relaxation time, and adhesion strength were determined enabling dynamic behaviour to be better understood.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Vanillin, 4-Aminophenol, benzyltriethylammonium chloride, (±)-epichlorohydrin, and 0.1N nitric acid in glacial acetic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Missouri, USA). Isopropanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, and methanol were purchased from Chem-supply. Diethyltoluenediamine, DETDA 100, was purchased from Huntsman Corporation (Everberg, Belgium).

2.2 Sample Preparation

The para-substituted epoxy imine, pVAPI, was synthesized by mixing vanillin (0.02 mol) and 4-aminophenol (0.02 mol) in 30% aqueous ethanol at 50°C for two hours according to the following reaction sequence in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Synthesis of pVAPI epoxy from vanillin and p-aminophenol.

The precipitate was filtered, washed with deionized water, and dried overnight in an oven at 60°C. Epoxidation of pVAPI was carried out by mixing pVAPI (0.02 mol), epichlorohydrin (0.10 mol) and

benzyltriethylammonium chloride catalyst (2 mol %). The mixture was refluxed at 90°C for 2 hours. A water isopropanol solution of sodium hydroxide (0.10 mol) then added and mixing continued for 2 hrs at 60°C. After filtering, the product was concentrated in vacuo at 100°C then washed several times with deionized water. Finally, pVAPI epoxide was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate, and then isolated in vacuo. The yield for pVAPI epoxy was 98%.

The resin systems were prepared by mixing pVAPI epoxide and DETDA together using epoxide to active hydrogen ratios of 1:0.5, 1:0.7, 1:0.9: 1:1.2 and 1:1.5. The formulations were degassed and mixed together at 120°C for 10 minutes then poured into pre-heated silicone moulds and cured in a convection oven at 120°C for 2 hours, 150°C for 2 hours and 177°C for 5 hours. DGEBA-DETD A formulations were prepared in a similar manner.

2.3 Characterization

Dynamic thermomechanical analysis was conducted with TA Q800 DMA. Samples with dimensions of 12×50×2.5 mm³ were prepared and placed in a dual cantilever fixture. A force amplitude of 15 μm with frequency of 1 Hz was applied from 30°C to 250°C at a rate of 3°C/min. The glass transition temperature, T_g , was determined from peak of the $\tan \delta$, and the crosslink density (ν_e) was calculated from the rubbery modulus, E_r , at $T_r = T_g + 50^\circ\text{C}$, and with R which is the real gas constant, using the equation,

$$\nu_e = E_r / (3RT_r) \quad (1)$$

Thermal stability and degradation studies were done with Netzsch TG 209 F1 Libra. Samples of about 5 mg were prepared in Al₂O₃ pans. The temperature was ramped from 30 to 800°C at 10°C/min under nitrogen. Samples were characterized based upon the temperature at 5% mass loss, $T_{5\%}$, the temperature at the maximum rate of degradation, T_{max} , and the char yield at 800°C.

Thermomechanical analysis was conducted with the Netzsch Hyperion TMA. Polymer samples were cut into 5 mm disks with a drill press and placed in between ceramic plates. A force of 0.05 N was applied to ensure good contact between the samples. The temperature was increased from 30°C to 270°C at 3°C/min. The coefficients of thermal expansion for the glassy and rubbery regions were calculated from the slope before and after the glass transition temperature.

Flexural testing were conducted using an Instron 68TM-50 Universal Testing Machine. Flexural tests was based on ASTM D790 wherein resin bars with dimensions 12×60×2.5 mm³ were prepared using a span-to-thickness ratio of 16:1, a crosshead displacement speed of 1.3 mm/min, and a 50 kN load cell. The modulus was measured from the slope of the stress–strain curve up to a flexural strain of 0.2%, and the flexural strength was measured from the maximum failure load.

To investigate test repeated adhesion, cured vitrimers placed on composite substrates were overlapped to an extent of 25 mm x 25 mm clamped together with a force of around 8 kN, and heated at 200°C for 3 hours in an oven. Adhesion was assessed according to a simple lap shear test using an Instron 5967 Universal Testing Machine

5 DISCUSSION

The cured resins are shown in Figure 2 illustrating the effect of stoichiometry on the colour of the cured resins. Clearly, imine networks become increasingly darker with higher levels of amine, reflecting the increasing vulnerability towards oxidation. In comparison the DGEBA DETDA networks are much less darker.

Figure 2: Images of the *p*VAPI-DETDA (left) and DGEBA-DETDA (right) networks after cure.

To evaluate the effect of stoichiometry on the thermomechanical properties of the vitrimer and non-vitrimer networks, dynamic mechanical analysis was performed. The DMTA spectra are shown in Figure 3 and the results are summarized in Table 1. Increasing amine content results in higher storage modulus and lower glass transition temperature which is also reflected in the lower crosslinking densities determined. All vitrimers have glass transition temperatures above 130°C, due to the rigid nature of the imine backbone. Unreacted amine groups led to a decrease in crosslinking density which is commonly observed in network polymers. The DMTA for the DGEBA DETDA networks had a higher storage modulus as well as lower glass transition temperature and crosslinking density.[10, 16] The tan delta peaks for all networks are symmetrical single peaks indicating homogeneous and fully cured networks formed even in the presence of excess epoxide and amine.

Figure 3: DMTA traces of the VAPI and DGEBA networks for 1:0.9 stoichiometry.

Thermomechanical analysis was performed to evaluate the effect of stoichiometry on the thermal expansion and dimensional stability. Figure 4 compares the raw thermogram from the DGEBA and *p*VAPI networks which show different behaviour. The DGEBA network appears quite standard with an inflection point corresponding to T_g , while the *p*VAPI imine does not appear to display an inflection point at T_g , again likely due to its rigid nature. The effect of stoichiometry on the CTE is shown in Table 1 where it can be seen that there is a gradual decrease in CTE with increasing amine content. In general the CTE of the DGEBA non vitrimer networks are lower than the vitrimer networks, suggesting it is more tightly constrained in the network.[10]

Figure 4: TMA traces of the VAPI and DGEBA networks for 1:0.9 stoichiometry.

The TGA thermograms show a typical mass loss transition in Figure 5. The important point to note is that the imine networks have a lower onset of degradation temperature and a high char yield compared to the DGEBA DETDA networks. As can be seen from the results, the effect of stoichiometry only has a modest impact upon degradation temperatures and char yields.[17]

Figure 5: TGA thermograms showing mass loss from decomposition of the cured pVAPI 1:0.9 and DGEBA 1:0.9 networks.

Table 1: Summary of the thermal and thermomechanical properties of pVAPI-DETDA and DGEBA-DETDA networks.

Network	DMA				TGA			TMA
	T _g ^a (°C)	T _g ^b (°C)	E' _{30°C} (GPa)	v _e ^c (10 ³ mol/m ³)	T _{5%} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	Char yield (%)	α _g (10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹)
pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.5	192	166	2.9	3.3	313	347	33	71
pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.7	179	150	3.4	5.2	312	351	29	72
pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.9	178	142	3.0	3.6	317	350	30	72
pVAPI-DETDA 1:1.2	147	126	3.2	2.2	316	348	27	69
pVAPI-DETDA 1:1.5	123	104	3.3	1.3	309	354	26	67
DGEBA-DETDA 1:0.5	73	61	3.0	0.04	295	388	9	80
DGEBA-DETDA 1:0.7	121	99	3.0	0.4	347	386	10	57
DGEBA-DETDA 1:0.9	173	153	2.0	1.3	369	386	9	59
DGEBA-DETDA 1:1.2	180	163	2.2	2.1	366	386	9	58
DGEBA-DETDA 1:1.5	146	134	2.3	1.0	363	388	8	49

^aDetermined by the peak of tan δ. ^bDetermined from the extrapolated onset of E'. ^cv_e is the crosslink density per unit volume from the DMA curves at T_g + 40°C.

The mechanical properties of the pVAPI and DGEBA networks are shown in Table 2 which highlight the effect of stoichiometry for both networks, the vitrimer and non-vitrimer. An example of the stress strain curve for the 1:0.9 stoichiometry in Figure 6 in particular highlights their brittle failure, particularly for pVAPI. For the pVAPI network, increasing amine content increases the modulus and strength but does not significantly affect the strain at break. These trends are opposite to that of the benchmark thermoset which exhibits decreasing modulus and strength as well as increasing strain at break with increasing amine content. During curing, bond exchange reactions may be activated by the high temperature needed for curing which relaxes internal stress and decreases defects in the network leading to better mechanical properties. Increasing the ratio increases the number of amines that can participate in transimination reactions resulting in higher flexural modulus and strength. However, the strain at break remains the same with increasing amine content. This could be due to the similar chemical composition of the vitrimers.[14]

Figure 6: Flexural stress-strain curves for the pVAPI and DGEBA 1:0.9 networks.

Table 2: Summary of the mechanical properties of pVAPI-DETDA and DGEBA-DETDA networks.

Network	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strain at Break (mm/mm)
pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.5	126	3.4	0.05
pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.7	150	3.9	0.05
pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.9	150	3.7	0.06
pVAPI-DETDA 1:1.2	155	3.9	0.06
pVAPI-DETDA 1:1.5	163	4.1	0.05
DGEBA-DETDA 1:0.5	30	3.3	0.01
DGEBA-DETDA 1:0.7	121	3.5	0.04
DGEBA-DETDA 1:0.9	122	2.9	0.08
DGEBA-DETDA 1:1.2	108	2.5	0.09
DGEBA-DETDA 1:1.5	95	2.7	0.11

Reversible or debondable adhesion of the vitrimers as a function of stoichiometry was investigated using lap shear. The load recovery is shown in Figure 7, where it can be seen that with increasing amine content, the load force increases. Clearly polymer chain diffusion and entanglement is therefore able to occur despite the fact that the polymer networks are fully cured. This highlights the molecular mobility of the imine functional group under heat and pressure. It is proposed that the dynamic covalent behaviour promotes transimination and imine metathesis between the surfaces enabling adhesion as the functional groups diffusion across the surfaces. Elevated temperatures increase the rate of these reversible exchange reactions that lead to topology rearrangements allowing faster chain diffusion. This experiment demonstrates the reprocessability of the VAPI vitrimer network while no diffusion for the DGEBA network was observed at all, despite efforts to do so. Figure 7 also shows the failure surfaces after re-processing highlight cohesive failure for stoichiometric and amine access networks.

Figure 7: (a) Lap shear applied force of pVAPI-DETDA networks after welding the cured resins at 200°C for 3 hours. (b) Lap shear failure images of pVAPI-DETDA 1:0.9 and 1:1.5.

9 CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the impact of epoxide-amine stoichiometry on the properties and reprocessability of a highly aromatic imine-based epoxy vitrimer. This research provides insight into the bond exchange mechanism as a function of amine content and its application to the development of a reversible or debondable adhesive. The vitrimer properties were highly tunable achieving T_g 's ranging from 120-210°C and flexural strength ranging from 120 to 160 MPa. This study is part of a broader study into the efficacy of imines as functional groups for high performance yet dynamic networks, and these results present excellent results that suggest that excellent mechanical and thermal properties, along with very good dynamic behaviour can go together in some high-performance networks.

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